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An Analysis on Students' Difficulties in Reading Aloud at The Eight Grade Students of MTs Negeri 2 Buol

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Abstract

This study analyzes the difficulties faced by eighth grade students at MTs Negeri 2 Buol in reading aloud. This research aims to identify challenges and provide insights into the difficulties students face in reading aloud. The study used qualitative methods, including observation and semi-structured interviews with students and English teachers. The results showed that the main difficulty students faced was lack of comprehension (79.16%), then followed by pronunciation difficulties (70.83%) then followed by slowing reading speed which was (62.5%), and finally anxiety at (54.16%). Pronunciation difficulties are also common, where students often focus too much on articulation and lack of vocabulary, leading to errors in word pronunciation. Lack of comprehension became a significant issue due to students' limited knowledge of what they read, which hindered their ability to present the material fluently. Lastly, anxiety plays an important role, with students experiencing excessive anxiety due to factors such as low self-confidence, fear of making mistakes, discomfort with their reading ability, and fear of being laughed at by peers if they make mistakes.

Keywords: *Reading Aloud, Students' Difficulties, Pronunciation, Reading Speed, Anxiety*

Abstrak

Penelitian ini menganalisis kesulitan yang dihadapi oleh siswa kelas delapan di MTs Negeri 2 Buol dalam membaca nyaring. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengidentifikasi tantangan dan memberikan wawasan mengenai kesulitan yang dihadapi siswa dalam membaca nyaring. Penelitian ini menggunakan metode kualitatif, termasuk observasi dan wawancara semi-terstruktur dengan siswa dan guru bahasa Inggris. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa kesulitan utama yang dihadapi siswa adalah kurangnya pemahaman (79,16%), diikuti oleh kesulitan pengucapan (70,83%), kemudian lambatnya kecepatan membaca (62,5%), dan terakhir kecemasan (54,16%). Kesulitan pengucapan juga umum terjadi, di mana siswa sering terlalu fokus pada artikulasi dan kekurangan kosakata, yang menyebabkan kesalahan dalam pengucapan kata. Kurangnya pemahaman menjadi masalah signifikan karena terbatasnya pengetahuan siswa tentang apa yang mereka baca, yang menghambat kemampuan mereka untuk menyajikan materi dengan lancar. Terakhir, kecemasan memainkan peran penting, dengan siswa mengalami kecemasan berlebihan akibat faktor-faktor seperti rendahnya kepercayaan diri, takut membuat kesalahan, ketidaknyamanan dengan kemampuan membaca mereka, dan takut ditertawakan oleh siswa lain jika mereka membuat kesalahan.

Kata kunci: *Membaca Nyaring, Kesulitan Siswa, Pengucapan, Pemahaman, Kecepatan Membaca, Kecemasan*

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INTRODUCTION

From pre-observation and interviews conducted on March 26, 2023, at MTs Negeri 2 Buol, regarding the problems faced by students in English lessons, one of the teachers explained the difficulties of the student at the eight grade of MTS Negeri 2 buol. The first was about the lack of student vocabulary. The students inability to read proficiently is caused by their limited vocabulary and structural knowledge. The students are also mostly difficult to pronounce the sentences. Because students' inability to read correctly makes them not so fluent in reading the text that has been provided.

As for other problems faced by students, some students stated that when it was their turn to read aloud in front of the class, they were unable to do so because they were embarrassed and lacked confidence. However, some students are able to read aloud in front of the class because they can read English texts, even if their pronunciation is not usually correct.

In the educational environment of MTs Negeri 2 Buol, it is imperative to understand the factors contributing to students' lack of proficiency in reading aloud. By gaining a deeper understanding of the underlying elements that contribute to this problem, teachers can design more effective approaches to find out what difficulties students face when reading aloud. Therefore, the present study was undertaken with the objective of finding out and explaining the challenges encountered by students at MTs Negeri 2 Buol in reading aloud. Therefore, this study aims to conduct an in-depth investigation into the issue of reading aloud within the context of MTs Negeri 2 Buol. The anticipated outcome is to provide a valuable contribution towards enhancing students' proficiency in the English language.

Based on the previous background, the researcher is interested in raising a case study entitled; "An Analysis On Student's Difficulties In Reading Aloud At The Eight Grade Student Of Mts Negeri 2 Buol"

METHOD

This study uses qualitative methods. Qualitative methods refer to the collection of descriptive data, both in written and spoken form, which can be utilized for the purpose of observing study (Huberman, 2014). Qualitative data can be collected by techniques such as observation, interviews, document analysis, and recording. According to Ary et al. (2010) Observation is the basic method for obtaining data in qualitative research. It is more global type of observation than the systematic, structured observation used in quantitative research. In analyzing students' difficulties in reading aloud, the researcher made observations in twenty four students in class VIII C MTs Negeri 2 Buol. According to (Creswell, 2012, p. 214) there are three types of interviews: face-to-face, phone, and cluster interviews. the research of use was conducted via telephone or interview, depending on the case. Structured and semi-structured interviews can be conducted. Structured interviews involve the interviewer asking the same questions to each respondent repeatedly. Semi-structured interviews (also known as targeted interviews) consist of a series of open-ended questions based on the subject area that the woman scientist needs to cover. In this case, according to (Sugiyono, 2016, p. 318) a semi-structured interview is an interview where the research subject can give free and unrestricted answers, but the subject must not deviate from the predetermined theme. the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with English teacher and students of class VIII C to identify the difficulties students face in reading aloud.

Data Analysis

Picture 1: *Flow Model of Qualitative Analysis*
(Adopted from Miles and Huberman's 1994)

In analyzing qualitative information, Bogdan (Sugiyono, 2016, p. 88) states that technique of analyzing data is method of systematic looking and compilation data that got from interviews, field notes, and alternative materials that simply understood and inform to others. In analysing the data, this study used qualitative flow model analysis projected by Miles & Huberman (1994). This model includes a triple flow of activities. They are information reduction, datashow and conclusion

Data reduction is the first step to accomplish in analyzing the research data. According to (Miles, 1994, p. 10), data reduction is the process of selecting, focusing, simplifying, abstracting, and transforming the data contained in written up field notes and transcripts. In this study, The data obtained were the results of interviews that were conducted with the students of class VIIIIC. In this step, the data taken from the interviews was condensed. In the process of selecting the data that had been obtained, it was directly selected according to the indicators of the problems studied. In the data focusing process, the selected data were focused on the four indicators studied. The next step was simplification, where the data that had been focused on the problem was simplified. The last step was data abstracting, where the data were abstracted for the next stage, namely data display. The second step is the display of data. According to Miles and Huberman (1994, p. 11), data display is a structured, condensed collection of information that enables conclusion drawing and action. As for this second step, after reducing the research interview data, the researcher displayed the data by showing the results of the interview data reductions. Just after the research data were reduced and displayed, the last step in the analysis is drawing conclusion.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The researcher collected data by conducting observations on twenty-four students and interviews with one English teacher and five students. In the observation, the researcher observed students who were reading in front of the class. Furthermore, in the interview, the researcher interviewed the English teacher of class VIIIIC and five students of class VIIIIC MTs Negeri 2 Buol. At that time, the researcher used an interview model called semi-structured interview. This type of interview is better for obtaining information because informants answer spontaneously from their experiences. In addition, observation and interview were chosen because of the flexibility of the data findings. On the findings in this study, the researcher only focused on finding the difficulties faced by students in reading aloud, which are four, namely slowing down reading speed, pronunciation difficulties, lack of comprehension, and anxiety.

Lack of comprehension	79.16%
Pronunciation difficulties	70.83%
Slowing down reading speed	62.5%
Anxiety	54.16%

According to Huang (2010: 148), there are four difficulties faced by students, namely slowing down reading speed, pronunciation difficulties, lack of comprehension, and anxiety. However, in this study, the arrangement of the explanation differs from the theory, because in this study it will be explained from the indicator that has the greatest difficulty experienced by students. And based on the results of the interview conducted by the researcher to the class teacher, most students have difficulties in reading aloud following the explanation.

The first difficulty based on theory is slowing down reading speed. However, the findings in this study show that the biggest difficulty faced by students is lack of comprehension as much as 79.16%. Lack of comprehension while reading refers to a person's difficulty in understanding or interpreting the content of the text being read. This can be caused by a variety of factors, including limited vocabulary, lack of understanding of concepts, or difficulty in assembling information cohesively. According to Peter, et al. (2008) Some factors that lead to poor comprehension are Limited vocabulary knowledge, lack of fluency, and limited familiarity with the subject. When someone experiences a lack of comprehension, they may struggle to extract the author's intended meaning or fail to connect the information with existing knowledge. In this case, the findings show that students' lack of comprehension in reading English text out of 24 students, 19 students or 79.16% did not understand

what they read, due to the limited vocabulary that students mastered. Limited vocabulary is a major obstacle in students' ability to present material fluently, so students tend not to understand what they read, which results in obstacles in presenting material with confidence. Some students stated that their lack of fluency in reading was due to unfamiliar English texts, so they felt less confident when presenting the material in front of the class.

Furthermore, the second difficulty faced by students is pronunciation difficulties. Based on previous research by (Novitasary, 2018), it shows that the most difficulties faced by tenth grade students of SMK Muhammadiyah 4 Surakarta are difficulties in pronunciation. However, the results of this study show that pronunciation difficulties are at number two after the lack of comprehension.

However, previous research conducted (Jufri, 2019) showed similar results to this study. Where Jufri's findings state that 70% of students make mistakes in pronunciation and the results of this study show the results of 70.83%. Pronunciation difficulties can affect students in reading in front of the class. According to (Huang, 2010) Students can have difficulty reading aloud due to limited vocabulary knowledge, which can cause difficulty in understanding and pronouncing unfamiliar words. Similar to the statement made by Huang, the results of interviews and observations showed that most students had difficulty in pronouncing English sentences. Also this study shows that many of the students tend to read English words according to their spelling, due to the limited vocabulary they know. and it is not uncommon for students not to read some words and even sentences because they do not know how to read them. Although there is variation in students' pronunciation ability, many still make mistakes. The teacher also noted that students who do not understand the meaning of words tend to have difficulty in pronouncing intonation correctly. Of the 24 students observed, 17 students or 70.83% had errors in word pronunciation, indicating a lack of vocabulary knowledge.

Research conducted by (Jufri, 2019) shows that the most difficulty is that 75% of students do not read fluently or read very slowly. And this is indeed in line with the theory that researchers use, namely the theory of (Huang, 2010) says that the first difficulty based on theory is slow reading speed. However, the results in this study show that slow reading speed is in the third position, namely 62.5% of students who are slow in reading. Slow reading can refer to a condition where a person has difficulties or limitations in processing text quickly. Factors such as difficulty understanding words, lack of concentration, or problems recognizing letters can cause the reading process to be slower than what is considered normal. The interview results show that students face the main problem of slow reading speed. According to (Huang, 2010), reading aloud in front of the class can be slow because students focus too much on articulation and lack vocabulary. This study found that one of the students' difficulties in reading aloud is the difficulty in pronouncing English words. students always read words based on it's spelling.

And the last one is anxiety. Reading anxiety refers to the level of anxiousness or tension that a person experiences when faced with the activity of reading. This anxiety can involve a variety of factors, such as fear of not being able to understand the text, lack of confidence in one's reading ability, or even fear of others' judgment of their reading ability. Such anxiety can affect a person's concentration and ability to understand and remember the information read. According to (Huang, 2010) Students can feel anxiety or embarrassment when reading aloud in front of others. Also in the findings (Novitasry, 2018) said students are afraid and nervous to pronounce words because students feel afraid of being wrong when pronouncing words.

Students often experience feelings of anxiety or embarrassment when asked to read aloud in front of peers or an audience. These feelings can significantly affect their performance and engagement in the task. The fear of making mistakes or stumbling over words can lead to feelings of insecurity, which causes their self-confidence to decrease. in this case, the results of this study showed that 13 students, or 54.16%, of the students had difficulty reading in front of the class because they faced excessive anxiety. Factors such as low self-confidence, fear of making mistakes in front of friends, because students are afraid that if they make mistakes they will be laughed at by other students, and discomfort with their reading ability can lead to feelings of embarrassment.

CONCLUSION

From the data analysis, The explanation above leads to the conclusion that students at MTSN 2 Buol experience the biggest difficulty in by lack of comprehension (79.16%) then followed by

pronunciation difficulties (70.83%) then followed by slowing down reading speed which is (62,5%) and finally anxiety at (54.16%) Factors such as difficulty understanding words can cause slow reading speed. Pronunciation difficulties are also common, with students often focusing too much on articulation and a lack of vocabulary, leading to errors in word pronunciation. Lack of comprehension becomes a significant issue due to students' limited knowledge of what they are reading, which hinders their ability to present the material fluently. Lastly, anxiety plays an important role, with students experiencing excessive anxiety due to factors such as low self-confidence, fear of making mistakes, discomfort with their reading ability, and fear of being laughed at by peers if they make wrongs. This can affect their performance when reading in front of the class.

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